

Aberrant Biosynthesis of (±)-, (+)- and (-)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatines†

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The incorporation of 2'-bromodidehydro[N-¹⁴CH₃]reticulium iodide (1) into (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4), (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (9) and (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7) in *Cocculus laurifolius* DC (Menispermaceae) has been studied and stereospecific reduction of 1 into (+)-9 and (-)-7 and (±)-4, 12-bromotetrahydropalmatines demonstrated.

Tetrahydropalmatine, a representative of 2,3,9,10-tetrasubstituted-tetrahydroprotoberberines, occurs in Nature in (±)-, (+)- and (-)-forms. (±)-Tetrahydropalmatine (5) has been isolated from many *Corydalis* species¹. (+)-Tetrahydropalmatine² (10) isolated first from *C. tuberosa* DC and *C. decumbens*, was subsequently isolated from several *Corydalis* species. (-)-Tetrahydropalmatine (8) first isolated from *C. aurea*, was isolated later on from *Stephania glabra*³ (Roxb.) Miers. The absolute configuration at the asymmetric centre 13a' in tetrahydroprotoberberines has been established by Corrodi and Hardegger⁴. It has been suggested that in general laevorotatory tetrahydroprotoberberines have *S*-configuration, whereas dextrorotatory tetrahydroprotoberberines have *R*-configuration at the asymmetric centre.

Tracer experiments have shown that (*R*)- and (*S*)-reticulines are specifically incorporated into (*R*)- and (*S*)-tetrahydropalmatines respectively⁵. (±)-Reticuline (3) is converted in the plants into (+)-tetrahydropalmatine (10). Further feeding of (±)-[1-³H, 4'-O-¹⁴CH₃]reticuline (3) showed

that reticuline is not converted into didehydroreticuline (2) in the plants and racemization of optically active forms of tetrahydropalmatine does occur via didehydrotetrahydropalmatine (6)⁵.

We have studied incorporation of 2'-bromodidehydroreticulium iodide (1) into (±)-(4), (+)-(9) and (-)-(7), 12-bromotetrahydropalmatines in *Cocculus laurifolius* DC (Menispermaceae) and demonstrated specific reduction of 1 into (+)-(9), (-)-(7) and (+)-(4), 12-bromotetrahydropalmatines respectively. The results of feeding experiments are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Precursor	% Incorporation into		
	(±)-form (4)	(+)-form (9)	(-)-form (7)
2'-Bromodidehydro- [N- ¹⁴ CH ₃]reticulium iodide (1)	0.27	0.12	0.15

2'-Bromodidehydro[N-¹⁴CH₃]reticulium iodide (1) was fed to twigs (9 nos) of *C. laurifolius* DC plants and the biosynthetic (±)-, (+)-, and (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatines 4, 9, 7 respectively, were found radioactive.

The regiospecificity of ¹⁴C label in the biosynthetic (±)-, (+)-, and (-)-, 12-bromotetrahydropalmatines derived from 2'-bromodidehydro[N-¹⁴CH₃]reticulium iodide was established as follows. Debromination of the biosynthetic (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4) with LAH furnished radioactive tetrahydropalmatine (5). Dehydrogenation of 5 with I₂ afforded labelled palmatine (11) with practically no loss of radioactivity. Grignard reaction of 11 with phenylmagnesium bromide yielded the radioactive 8-phenyldihydropalmatine (12). Chromic acid oxidation (Kuhn-Roth) of 12 gave radioactive benzoic acid (92% of original activity).

The biosynthetic (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (9) was debrominated with LAH to afford the labelled tetrahydropalmatine (10). Dehydrogenation of 10 with I₂ yielded

†Dedicated to honour Dr. Sukh Dev for his outstanding contributions to organic chemistry and to the cause of the Indian Chemical Society.

11. Treatment of 11 with phenylmagnesium bromide furnished labelled 12. Kuhn-Roth oxidation of 12 gave radioactive benzoic acid (96% of original activity).

The biosynthetic (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7) was debrominated with LAH to give 8. Dehydrogenation of 8 with I₂ furnished 11. Treatment of 11 with phenylmagnesium bromide yielded 12. Kuhn-Roth oxidation of 12 furnished radioactive benzoic acid (93% of original activity).

The foregoing tracer experiments thus established that the enzyme system present in *C. laurifolius* DC is capable of converting 2'-bromodidehydroreticulium salt (1) into (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (9) and (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7); (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4) is perhaps formed by mixing of (+)-9 and (-)-7 forms during isolation. The carbon atom 8 of 12-bromotetrahydropalmatines is formed by oxidative cyclization of N-CH₃ function of 2'-bromoreticulines.

Experimental

Unless stated otherwise uv spectra of the compounds were taken in ethanol, ir spectra in KBr and nmr spectra in deuteriochloroform. Tlc was carried out, unless specified to the contrary, on silica GF-254.

Counting methods : Liquid scintillation counting was used for the measurement of ¹⁴C activity (Packard 314 Ex instrument). Radioactive samples were dissolved in methanol or dimethylformamide (0.2 ml) and liquid scintillator (7 ml); quoted activities were not corrected for self-absorption except where stated. The relative efficiencies were obtained by counting [2-¹⁴C]-hexadecane standard.

2'-Bromo[N-¹⁴CH₃]-dehydroreticulium iodide (1) : 2'-Bromodidehydro-*O,O*-dibenzylreticuline was synthesized by the standard procedure⁶. A solution of the dehydro-

isoquinoline in dry C₆H₆ was added to frozen [¹⁴C]CH₃I and the mixture was kept at 0° for 2 days. Inactive CH₃I was then added to the mixture to complete the reaction. The resulting mixture was worked up in the usual manner to afford 2'-bromodidehydro[N-¹⁴CH₃]-*O,O*-dibenzylreticulium iodide. Hydrogenolysis of the salt with methanolic hydrochloric acid finally furnished labeled 2'-bromodidehydro[N-¹⁴CH₃]reticulium iodide (1).

Resolution :

(+)-Tetrahydropalmatine (10) : (±)-Tetrahydropalmatine (5; 2.8 g) in MeOH (30 ml) was treated with di-*p*-toluoyl-*d*-tartaric acid (2.0 g) in MeOH (35 ml). The resulting salt was fractionally crystallized from C₆H₆ (10 times) and then from MeOH (10 times) to give the crystalline salt (1.2 g), m.p. 149°; [α]_D +68° (c, 2.0, EtOH). The salt in H₂O (5 ml) was treated with 4 *N* NaOH (20 ml). The liberated base was extracted with CHCl₄ (4 × 20 ml), washed with H₂O, dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to afford (+)-tetrahydropalmatine (10; 420 mg), m.p. 141–42°; [α] +292° (c, 1.8, EtOH) (lit.² m.p. 142°; [α]_D +292.5°, EtOH).

(-)-Tetrahydropalmatine (8) : Partially resolved tetrahydropalmatine (1.3 g) in MeOH, enriched with (-)-enantiomer was treated with di-*p*-toluoyl-*l*-tartaric acid (630 mg) in MeOH (15 ml). The solvent from the resulting salt was removed and the residue fractionally crystallized first with C₆H₆ and then with MeOH to give the crystalline salt, m.p. 154°; [α]_D -78° (c, 1.3, EtOH) which was decomposed with 4 *N* NaOH. The base was extracted with CHCl₃ and crystallized from MeOH to yield (-)-tetrahydropalmatine (8), m.p. 142°; [α]_D -29.1° (c, 0.9, EtOH) (lit.⁷ m.p. 141–42°; [α]_D -290.8°, EtOH).

(±)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatine (4) : To a stirred solution of (±)-tetrahydropalmatine (5; 800 mg) in 10% AcOH (25 ml) at 5° was added a solution of bromine in AcOH (10%; 4 ml) and stirring continued for 1.5 h. The mixture was then heated at 100° for 3 h, poured into H₂O containing sodium metabisulphite, acidified with AcOH and extracted with Et₂O (3 × 15 ml). The aqueous acidic solution was basified (pH 8) with Na₂CO₃ and extracted with CHCl₃ (6 × 25 ml). The combined CHCl₃ extract was washed with H₂O, dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄), the solvent removed and the product chromatographed on a silica gel column. Elution of the column with C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (3 : 1) afforded (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4; 440 mg), m.p. 160–61° (MeOH) (lit.⁶ 161–62°).

(+)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatine (9), m.p. 159–60° (MeOH); [α]_D +202° (c, 1.9, EtOH) and (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7), m.p. 158–59° (MeOH); [α]_D -207° (c,

2.26, EtOH) were similarly prepared.

Feeding experiments :

Labeled 2'-bromo[N - ^{14}C]₃didehydroreticulinium iodide (1) was dissolved in aq. dimethyl sulphoxide (1 ml) and fed to twigs (12 nos) of *Cocculus laurifolius* DC (Menispermaceae) by stem-cut technique when uptake of the precursor was complete, H₂O added to wash the precursor. The twigs were then dipped in H₂O and kept alive for 7 days to metabolise the precursor.

Biosynthetic (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4) : The twigs (12 nos) (240 g wet wt.) of *C. laurifolius*, fed with the labeled precursor, were divided into three parts. One part (82 g) was macerated in EtOH (250 ml) with radio-inactive (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4; 105 mg). EtOH from the macerated plant material was decanted and the residual plant material was percolated with fresh EtOH (4 × 200 ml). The combined percolate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give a greenish viscous mass which was extracted with 2% HCl (5 × 10 ml). The combined aqueous acidic extract was defatted with pet. ether (4 × 15 ml), basified (pH 8) with Na₂CO₃ and the liberated base extracted with CHCl₃ (5 × 20 ml). The combined CHCl₃ extract was washed with H₂O, dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The crude base, thus obtained, was subjected to preparative tlc on silica gel GF 254 plates (solvent : CHCl₃-MeOH, 99 : 1). The region containing the desired base was cut and eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (80 : 20). The solvent from the eluate was removed and the base crystallized from MeOH to furnish radioactive (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4; 80 mg), m.p. 160–61° (lit.⁶ 161–62°).

Biosynthetic (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (9) : The twigs (4 nos; 85 g) of *C. laurifolius* DC were macerated in EtOH (250 ml) with radio-inactive (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (10; 100 mg) and worked up as above to give the crude base, crystallized from MeOH to yield radioactive (+)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (9; 75 mg), m.p. 159–60°; [α]_D +20° (c, 1.5, EtOH).

Biosynthetic (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7) : The twigs (4 nos; 80 g) of *C. laurifolius* DC were macerated in EtOH (200 ml) with radio-inactive (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7; 100 mg) and worked up in the usual manner to give the crude base, crystallized from MeOH to furnish radioactive (-)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (7; 70 mg), m.p. 158–60°; [α]_D -207° (c, 2.26, EtOH).

Degradation of the biosynthetic (±)-12-bromo[8- ^{14}C]tetrahydropalmatine (4) derived from 2'-bromodidehydro[N - ^{14}C]₃reticulinium iodide (1) : A solution of the biosynthetic (±)-12-bromotetrahydropalmatine (4; 340 mg)

in dry THF (7 ml) was added to a stirred suspension of LAH (550 mg) in dry THF (5 ml) at 55° and the stirring continued for 4 h. The resulting mixture was worked up in the usual manner to give a product which was purified on a neutral Al₂O₃ column. The purified base, thus obtained, was crystallized from MeOH to give radioactive (±)-tetrahydropalmatine (5; 280 mg), m.p. 148° (lit.¹ 147.5–48.5°).

The radioactive base 5 (275 mg) in EtOH (5 ml) was refluxed with I₂ (280 mg) to yield radioactive palmatine (11; 110 mg), m.p. 238–39° (lit.⁷ 239–40°). Radioactive base 11 in dry Et₂O was treated with PhMgBr to furnish radioactive 8-phenyldihydropalmatine (12; 75 mg), m.p. 158–59° (lit.⁸ 158–60°). The labeled base 12 was oxidized with chromic acid (Kuhn-Roth) to yield finally radioactive benzoic acid. The radioactivity of the compounds is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compd	Molar activity × 10 ⁵ disint min ⁻¹ mmol ⁻¹
(±)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatine (4)	1 10
(±)-Tetrahydropalmatine (5)	1 07
Palmatine (11)	1 03
8-Phenyldihydropalmatine (12)	1 05
Benzoic acid	1 02

Degradation of the biosynthetic (+)-12-bromo[8- ^{14}C]tetrahydropalmatine (9) derived from 2'-bromodidehydro[N - ^{14}C]₃reticulinium iodide (1) : The biosynthetic (+)-12-bromo[8- ^{14}C]tetrahydropalmatine (9; 345 mg) was degraded as above. Debromination of radioactive base 9 with LAH yielded radioactive (+)-tetrahydropalmatine (10). Dehydrogenation of radioactive 10 with I₂ afforded radioactive palmatine 11. Treatment of 11 with PhMgBr gave radioactive 12. Kuhn-Roth oxidation of radioactive 12 yielded radioactive benzoic acid. The radioactivity of the compounds is recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Compd	Molar activity × 10 ⁴ disint min ⁻¹ mmol ⁻¹
(+)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatine (9)	5 00
(+)-Tetrahydropalmatine (10)	4 96
Palmatine (11)	4 88
8-Phenyldihydropalmatine (12)	4 90
Benzoic acid	4 80

Degradation of the biosynthetic (-)-12-bromo[8- ^{14}C]tetrahydropalmatine (7) derived from 2'-bromodidehydro[N - ^{14}C]₃reticulinium iodide (1) : The biosynthetic (-)-12-bromo[8- ^{14}C]tetrahydropalmatine (7) was degraded as above. Debromination of the biosynthetic base

TABLE 4

Compd.	Molar activity $\times 10^4$ disint. min^{-1} mmol^{-1}
(-)-12-Bromotetrahydropalmatine (7)	5.85
(-)-Tetrahydropalmatine (8)	5.72
Palmatine (11)	5.60
Benzoic acid	5.45

(7; 340 mg) with LAH gave radioactive base 8 which on dehydrogenation with I_2 furnished the radioactive palmatine 11. Treatment of radioactive 11 with PhMgBr yielded radioactive base 12. Kuhn-Roth oxidation of the radioactive base 12 gave radioactive benzoic acid. The radioactivity of the compounds is recorded in Table 4.

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